
Socio-Economic Status of Fisherwomen in Kashmir: A Study on Hanji Community of Wular Lake

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ABSTRACT

This paper is a study of the socio-economic conditions of fisherwomen of Hanji community living around the Wular Lake. The focus of the paper is on the examining the role and decision making power of fisherwomen and to know their health issues as well. The study was performed on 100 fisherwomen from the village of the Bandipora district in Kashmir valley. Data collection method used in the research was "Interview Schedule". In the Hanji community, Fishing isn't just a livelihood for the men but women also play a crucial role in the fisheries sector, actively contributing to the industry by selling the fish products, thus, they create an essential link between the producers and the consumers. In contempt of their active role in fishing activities, their contributions are neither recognized nor quantified and are still being isolated, unorganised and are considered the disadvantaged group in our society which constraints their personal as well as professional life. Besides these drawbacks they are also facing health issues due to unhygienic environment of the occupation.

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Introduction

“No society can develop fully without a significant contribution of women towards its development. It must be clear to that half a nation; i.e. only men can't create a modern society”.

Kamla Bhasin Kapoor

Fishing is an ancient and significant occupation which also contributes to the Indian economy (Immanuel and Rao 2009). Fisheries have long been a supplementary activity for fishing communities, often practiced at a subsistence level (Krishnan et al., 2000). In numerous developing countries, the fisheries sector is vital for providing employment and income, helping to reduce poverty and improve food security (FAO, 1997; Thilsted, 1997; Katiha et al., 2017). The International Collective in Support of Fishworkers (ICSF, 2010) emphasizes that fisheries serve as a vital source of livelihood for millions of people globally. India ranks second in global fish production, following China, with a production of 7.3 million tons in 2007 (FAO, 2009). The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) estimates that approximately 35 million people are directly engaged in fishing & aquaculture worldwide. As per FAO (2000), Asia is home to the largest proportion of fishermen and aquaculture workers, accounting for 85% of the global total, followed by Africa at 7%, and smaller shares in Europe, South America, North and Central America (around 2% each), and Oceania (0.2%). According to FAO, 2008 fisheries is a growing sector in the economy of Jammu and Kashmir which has experienced persistent growth over the past decades. Fishing is a major industry in India's coastal states but the coastal fish workers have always been one of the India's most vulnerable groups among the poor. Fisheries sector is one of the important food production sectors that significantly contribute to the livelihood and food security to a large section of the economically underprivileged population in all the states (Biswas and Rao, 2014). Fisheries sector is a key sector of the Indian economy where women make substantial contributions. The socioeconomic condition of the fisherwomen in India is very poor and is confronted with many problems (Nalatham, 2019). This profession usually includes both sexes and helps one another to develop their economies and their lives (Khader, 2019). Fisherwomen play a vital role in fulfilling both household and community needs. (Karthikesan et al., 2019), and their issues are also countless. The fishing sector does not provide a consistent source of income throughout the year and the marketing of fish is performed on a high level during the seasons. Fishermen face significant hardship during the off-season, struggling to cover their personal and family expenses. (Jamuna, 2016). Due to technological failures and natural hazards fishing occupation is considered a risky profession (Smith, 1998). Fishing is like a lottery catch and is different from day to day, from week to week. One day you get plenty of catch, but you may suffer poorly or even no catch on subsequent days (Islam and Chuenpagde, 2013).

Fishing is a crucial sector for employment and income generation in many countries worldwide. It plays an essential role in supporting livelihoods and provides a primary source of nutrition for over one billion people globally (Ghosh et al., 2015). From a developmental perspective, fisheries are prioritized in national agendas, especially because they support large segments of the population that are considered disadvantaged. In national development programs, the fisheries sector holds significant importance, contributing to foreign exchange earnings, meeting domestic consumption needs, and promoting equity in poverty reduction strategies (Sathiadhas, 2009).

In Kashmir, the fishing community has traditionally been marginalized and considered a disadvantaged group in society. As a result, they have often been isolated and unorganized, with a reluctance to interact openly with other communities or trades. Fishing, viewed culturally as a male-dominated activity, has often overshadowed the important contributions of women. However, understanding the important contributions of women in this sector, both historically and in the present day, reveals their significant involvement. In fisher families, women not only manage household responsibilities but also play a vital role in the growth and development of the fisheries sector. They perform a variety of roles, including those related to livelihood, reproduction, household management, and community engagement. Despite their active participation in both capture and culture fisheries, women's contributions across different stages of production, including harvesting and post-harvest activities, are often overlooked. While their roles in the fisheries sector are vital, they remain largely unrecognized and unarticulated (Dehadrai, 2002). As seen in other parts of the world, fisherwomen in India make significant contributions within the fishing communities, often managing family affairs when the men are at sea, working to ensure the family's survival.

In Kashmir, fisherwomen are known as Gadhi-wajni and are considered to be the oldest Kashmiri's entrepreneurs even though modernisation ruled the roost they retained their individuality. In Kashmir, fish marketing carries a social stigma, and those involved in it, particularly within the fishing community, are often looked down upon by the wider society. The role of fisherwomen in this context is greatly impacted by the socio-economic circumstances of their households. Beyond selling fish in the market or going door to door, fisherwomen play an essential role as homemakers, providing crucial support that allows men to focus on other livelihood activities. Their responsibilities include managing household tasks such as cooking, childcare, children's education, and ensuring family health and sanitation, all of which are vital to the well-being of the family. Different research studies have shown that women play an important role in post-harvest fisheries activities such as fish marketing and

processing (Immanuel and Rao 2009). Women are directly involved in various activities within the fisheries sector, such as cleaning, fish trading, and fish curing. Indirectly, they also play a crucial role in decision-making, financial management, and ensuring family welfare (Ashaletta, et al., 2002).

Profile of the study area

Wular Lake, one of Asia's largest freshwater lakes, is located in the districts of Bandipora and Baramulla in the Indian Union Territory of Jammu and Kashmir and known for its stunning beauty and rich biodiversity, it plays a vital role in the region's ecology and economy. It lies approximately 60 kilometers from Srinagar city, at a latitude of 34°16' to 34°26' N and longitude of 74°32' to 74°42' E, with an elevation of 5,180 meters above sea level (Dar et al., 2014). The deepest part of the lake is referred to as "Mota Khon" or the 'Gulf of Corpses.' The lake is sustained by the waters of three major rivers: Madhumati, Erin, and Jhelum. These rivers not only supply water to the lake but also play a crucial role in maintaining its ecological balance and supporting the diverse wildlife and communities around it. The Jhelum River enters the lake at Banyari, about 40 kilometers from Srinagar, and then branches off at Ningli. Wular Lake is crucial for the livelihood of the surrounding population, with 31 villages in the Baramulla and Bandipora districts depending on it for sustenance (Census of India, 2001). This study was carried out in the Bandipora district, often referred to as the 'fish bowl' of the state, due to its significance as a major fish-producing region in the valley. There are 20 fishing villages in district Bandipora out of which 5 villages were selected randomly. These villages depend directly or indirectly on the Wular Lake for their sustenance. From each village 20 fisherwomen were selected. Thus total number of fisherwomen selected was 100.

In district Bandipora, these 20 fishing villages are situated close to the Wular Lake. The villages around Wular Lake have been predominantly inhabited by fishermen's families for generations. The people in these villages are typically conservative and often live below the poverty line (Govt. of Jammu & Kashmir, 2016-17). The majority of the population relies on the lake for their livelihood. The researcher gathered this information during a survey conducted between December 2018 and March 2019. The social and economic backwardness of these villages have strengthened their poor status. The people of the study areas earn their livelihood only from fishing. Both male and females are equally involved in fishing activities, contributing to various aspects of the trade and sustaining the livelihood of their communities. Poverty and economic hardships compels fisherwomen to step out of their homes to sell fish. The living conditions of fisherwomen in the study area are far from satisfactory, as they face

difficulties at every stage of their lives, struggling with challenges in both their personal and professional lives.

The people of these villages are disadvantaged group of the society and are neglected one. They face numerous challenges both in their work and in their daily lives. In context of development these villages are very weak, they prefer to do labor activity rather than gaining education. Approximately 95% of the population depends on Wular Lake for a variety of resources, while 90% of women are engaged in fish trade and fish processing, playing a vital role in the local economy.

Methodology

The study seeks to examine the socio-economic status of fisherwomen from the Hanji community around Wular Lake in the Bandipora district, identify the challenges they face in the marketplace, and address the health issues they encounter. The research focuses on 20 fishing villages, of which five villages—Laharwalpora, Kulhuma, Kemah, Parebal, and Sogam Wudar—were selected using a random sampling method. This study specifically targets the fisherwomen in these five villages, where a significant number of people are involved in fishing activities. Data were collected from the fisherwomen over a span of three months. For the study the important variables were age, family system, marital status, income level and educational level. For determining the socio-economic status of fisherwomen these variables were considered very important. The data collected from respondents were tabulated according to the variables studied. An interview schedule has been constructed to collect data by using the purposive sampling method among of 100 fisherwomen of five villages in district Bandipora. Researcher followed fisherwomen from their homes in the early morning as they went to the places transported the fish to the market. Each interview lasted about 25 minutes on average and the responses were handwritten by a researcher because some fisherwomen felt uncomfortable with tape recording.

Women's participation in Fisheries Sector

Traditionally, in Kashmir, fisherwomen have had an important role in the fishing industry, extending beyond just selling fish and using traditional fish processing methods. They actively participate in the actual fishing operations, working alongside men. In Kashmir, "Fisherwomen play a crucial role in the fisheries business, participating daily in the distribution and sale of the fish catch. Apart from their duties as housewives, these women engage in a variety of activities, including catching, processing (such as salting and drying), and marketing fish, as well as hand-braiding fishing nets. On average, they

spend 6 to 9 hours a day on these tasks, generating a substantial income that contributes to the household economy (Rather and Bhat, 2017).

The contribution of fisherwomen in the post-harvest sector has been well-documented by various researchers (Kohli et al., 1999), highlighting that fish handling, processing, and marketing heavily depend on women. However, they also face several challenges, including the lack of cold storage facilities, appropriate fish preservation technologies, and the rising costs of fish production (Durai and Dhanalakshmi, 2015). Besides their household management roles, fisherwomen significantly contribute to the development of the fisheries sector (Jadhav and Deshmukh, 2014). They bear the responsibility for maintaining the social, cultural, and economic fabric of their communities while also handling reproductive tasks, all while frequently being exposed to various challenges (Sharma, 2011).

Once the fish are caught, fisherwomen take charge of tasks such as sales, drying, processing, and other related activities. They play an essential role in selling fish, which generates considerable income for their households. Many fisherwomen report using their earnings to invest in building homes (20%), purchasing land (15%), or saving (38%). A smaller percentage invests in buying vehicles (8%) or livestock (4%). While the actual fishing is carried out by men in the study area, activities like washing, processing, and marketing the fish are primarily handled by women (Premapriya and Jeyaseelan, 2019).

In the study area, most women walk to nearby villages to sell fish, and their earnings vary depending on the type of fish sold. They typically earn a profit of Rs. 200-250 per day. However, they face numerous challenges, such as fluctuating market prices, unhygienic marketplaces, and a lack of basic amenities. In fact, 78% of women in the area are involved in fish marketing (Selvaraj, 2000). Despite the significant role they play, fisherwomen face a variety of daily difficulties. They dedicate most of their day to fish marketing, in addition to performing household chores like cooking and collecting water. While many are hopeful of improving their lives through the development of the fisheries sector and are eager to acquire new skills, poverty and, to some extent, ignorance continue to impede their progress.

Table 1: Role of Fisherwomen in Different Activities

Activities	No. of Respondents	Role of Fisherwomen (%)
Fish selling	78	78%
Salting/Curing/Drying	22	22%
Total	100	100

Source: Primary data

As table 1.revealed that almost 78.00 per cent of the fisherwomen were engaged in fish marketing and 22.00 per cent were involved in salting, drying and curing. Side by side they also were engaged in household chores.

Status of Fisherwomen

A woman's status is often determined by various factors, including her income, employment, education, health, fertility, and her roles within the family, community, and society. In India, the Vedic period is often seen as a golden era for women's status, as they enjoyed significant rights during this time (Manzoor, 2012). In fishing communities, the role of women is particularly substantial and vital. Fisherwomen hold more importance in these communities than in many other social groups because of their intense labor, as the family's economy and management largely depend on them. Even with the rise of industrialization and the commercialization that impacted the fishing economy, women have continued to play a crucial role and contribute significantly to their family’s income.

Work related problems

In addition to the general challenges faced by the poor in underdeveloped regions in their daily lives, women in the fishing community encounter specific issues in their work lives. The problems faced by the fisherwomen in the study area are as follows (Table 2):

Table 2: Rank wise work related problems faced by fisherwomen

Work related problems	Order in rank
Lack of work in lean season	I
Physical strain in carrying fish to the market	II
Low income	III
Exploitation by middlemen	IV

Source: Primary data

As stated by the fisherwomen “lack of work in the lean season” is a major problem. The women remain unemployed when there is no fishing and don’t have any alternate employment. In the study area, the lack of land prevents women from starting income-generating enterprises such as agriculture, dairying, or poultry farming. Additionally, women in the area report experiencing physical strain from carrying fish to the market, as they often have to walk 2 to 3 kilometers to sell their catch, either in the local

market or by going from street to street. This task is both challenging and exhausting for them. Further they also complain about low income and find hard to run their households. Sometimes they are also exploited by the middlemen.

Women's Role in Decision Making

The ability to make decisions is crucial for the empowerment of fisherwomen, as their voices are often not given proper attention or consideration within the community. This lack of decision-making power hinders their ability to influence their own lives and the broader fishing industry. It has been said that in family matters if an individual has a say then it is a strong step towards empowerment. The decision making power of women should not be ignored. The real development cannot take place without active participation of fisherwomen. So in the present study, the involvement of women in decision making in the economic and social spheres, both at household and community level was examined. The role of the men and women are clearly demarcated in the study area as the man has to do catching and a woman has to do marketing. To determine the women's status in the family this thing is considered an important area. A same study was done by Nayak (1993), he found in his study that fisherwomen contributed a major portion of the family income. But in this present study researcher found the same thing and men played a major role in decision making power.

Over the decades, the role of women in decision making seems to have changed substantially. The researcher found out in the study that men are playing dominant roles in the decision making process. In social functions, men still play a dominant role in decision making. At the time of marriage of their children 5 per cent women were consulted for their opinion. In the study area women make decisions in selling of fishes and sometimes home management too. Research studies show that decision making has a direct relation to the work that people do. Anitha (2002) reported the same. In household decisions 80 per cent women are playing its role in purchase of food and clothes and other things and have full control over the money that they earn.

Fisherwomen and poor social acceptance

In the fisheries sector, women spend long hours performing time-consuming and labour-intensive tasks (Srivastava, 1985). These demanding workloads leave them with little time for rest, leisure, or engaging in other activities. Fish selling is predominantly carried out by women. Despite their significant involvement, their invaluable contributions are often overlooked and underreported, leading to a lack of proper working conditions, facilities, training, and access to information for them. Although women

play a crucial role in contributing to the economy and household income, their socio-economic status remains significantly lower than that of men.

Experience of Working as Fisherwomen and Fish Processors

Experience is a key factor influencing a person's ability to succeed in the fishing business. The more experience a respondent has, the more skilled they become in fishing and fish processing. In the study area, respondents have an average of 10 years of experience in salted fish processing to make a living. Most respondents have between 11 to 50 years of experience as fish processors, accounting for 28.8% of the group. Additionally, respondents' experience as fishermen ranges from 4 to 10 years. Fishermen in the area have developed the skills necessary to go to sea, search for fish, and adapt to challenges such as climate change, weather conditions, and technological advancements in fish catching.

The Multiple Roles of Fisherwomen

Women are often seen as oppressed due to their heavy workload and the societal attitudes that continue to reinforce the burden placed on them. When examining their daily activities in detail, it becomes clear that women take on multiple roles and responsibilities. In addition to their work in the fisheries sector, all women are responsible for unpaid household tasks such as cleaning, washing clothes, preparing meals, and child-rearing. These duties, while essential, further contribute to the physical and emotional strain women experience. I interviewed fisherwomen and ask them regarding their multiple roles and they described her day as follows: *Zubaida, I have started this type of work when I was 12 years old. I used to sell fish door to door or head load fish and for some of many clients I even cut the fish for them as they don't want to touch the fish. I sometimes directly sell the fish in the market. I get up at 3:30 in the morning and that I have to wait for my husband to return with a catch of fish. I usually return home late evening from the market. Once I reached my home I have to do all the household chores and making the evening meal.*

Another respondent Sara revealed that "I roamed in all the streets with head load of fish which is a very tiresome activity. Health complications are the result of such marketing and said that I have to do all the domestic chores as well but I managed and also stated that I do not have interest to do any other job. I never faced any abuse from my husband and often facing some problems from the customers in the form of bargaining. She also reiterated that physical and mental exhaustion were experienced due to head load of fish".

Another respondent **Rafiq** from the study area, a mother of four daughter said that “I have been marketing fish for almost 12 years. I have learnt from my mother in law how to deal with customers and motivate them to buy my fish on genuine rates, but the quality matters a lot. There are many people who trust the quality of my fish, since I never cheat them”.

One more respondent **Nahida** narrated that “I don’t have alternate job because we don’t have land for agricultural purposes as we are water dwellers. Our wages are crucial part of our family income. I for my family have to do hard work to sustain our life and don’t have much resource like other people of Kashmir’s have. In our community men’s job is to catch fish and we are dealing with market to make our living sustain and being a women we are responsible for work both inside and outside the home and still our position is same in our society”.

General Findings

The present study is mainly intended to examine the socio-economic status of fisherwomen in Bandipora district. Many constraints are faced by the fisherwomen invariably across the nation and Jammu & Kashmir is no exception. In this paper socio-economic status of fisherwomen have been highlighted and discussed in detail. It has been revealed by the study that many women took up fish marketing profession either to continue their family business or to supplement their husband’s income or to make provision for the future financial security of their children. Fisheries sector of Kashmir valley has lot of potential for growth and development. However the main stakeholders i.e. the fisherwomen are beset with many constraints. These constraints in one or the other way have prevented the growth and developments of these fisherwomen to a great extent. While interviewing the fisher women revealed some of the major obstacles and constraints faced by the fisherwomen are mentioned below.

Table 3: Problems faced by the fisherwomen while selling fishes

S.No.	Face any problem while selling fishes	No. of Respondents	Percentage
01	Yes	80	80%
02	No	20	20%
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary data

Table 3 revealed that 80.00 per cent fisherwomen were facing problem while selling fishes. Then 20.00 per cent were not facing problems during marketing of fishes. They explained that we face transport problems as well as fish unavailability.

Table 4: Educational Status of the Fisherwomen

S.No.	Educational Qualification	No.ofRespondents	Percentage
01.	Literate	20	20%
02.	Illiterate	80	80%
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary data

Illiteracy is prevalent among the fisherwomen in particular. During survey literacy percentage was found to be very low. Fisherwomen were mostly found illiterate and table 4. Reveals that only 20.00 per cent respondents were literate and 80.00 per cent were illiterate. Majority of the respondents revealed that poverty, lack of schools in the vicinity and lack of awareness about the educational benefits and were many more reasons given by the fisher women for being illiterate. During survey, literacy rate among the females was found to be negligible due to ignorance and orthodox views of the fishers about female education and mostly boys are sent to schools and girls are being kept at home.

Table 5: Age wise distribution of Fisherwomen

Age	No. of Respondents	Percentage
25-30	10	10%
30-35	16	16%
35-40	50	50%
Above 40	24	24%
Total	100	100

Source: Primary data

Sociologically, age denotes the status of an individual in a group, be that his family, kinship or other larger and organized groups of society. From the survey, table 5 reveals that 50.00 per cent of the respondents are in the age group of 35-40 years, 16.00 per cent of the respondents are in the age group of 30-35 years and 24.00 per cent of the respondents belong in the age group above 40 years and remaining 10.00 per cent of the respondents in the age group 25-30 years.

Table 6: Marital Status of the Respondents

Marital Status	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Married	90	90%
Unmarried	10	10%

Total	100	100
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Source: Primary data

During the survey the researcher found out that 90.00 per cent of the respondents were married and 10.00 per cent of the respondents were unmarried. The study found out that married respondents are highly involved in marketing of fish in these five villages. In the study area early marriages are still happening and girls are not given freedom to select their life partners. The study revealed that they invest good amount on marriage celebrations.

Table 7: Family system of the Respondents

Family System	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Joint family	80	80%
Nuclear family	20	20%
Total	100	100

Source: Primary data

Table 7 revealed that 20.00 per cent of the respondents are from nuclear family and remaining 80.00 per cent of the respondents are belongs to joint family.

Table 8: Monthly Income of the Respondents

Monthly income	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1500-3000	60	60%
3001-4000	40	40%
Total	100	100

Source: Primary data

The data showed that 60.00 per cent of the respondents having the monthly income between Rs. 1500-3000 and remaining 40.00 per cent of the respondents have got the monthly income 3001-4000

Health related issues and time utilisation

The status of health is the reflection of livelihood status. The facilities of the health enjoyed by the fisherwomen in the study area were not at all good. Generally, fisherwomen suffer from malnutrition and dietary imbalance and take medicine from unskilled, non-professional village doctors. Fisherwomen in the study area reported that they suffered from knee pain and back pain. The nature of work and socio-economic condition warrants their life. The tedious work nature made their health as worsen. Being women, they are in the position to look after their respective family. They face discrimination in

the case of health care. There are no proper sanitation facilities in the market and this affects their health. During the survey these villages dominated by fishers were found to be quite unhygienic. The fisherwomen revealed that they were looked down by the rest of the society. Unhygienic living conditions are one of the reasons for the deep rooted social stigma towards this community. In today's world, women take on a variety of roles in society, and this is particularly evident in the fisheries sector. They often juggle multiple tasks at once, which puts them at risk of work-related diseases and hazards. These challenges are compounded by social, psychological, and physiological issues, making their workload even more demanding and detrimental to their well-being.

Fisherwomen in the study area stated that they spend 5-6 hours in marketing of fishes and 20 per cent of their time spends on fetching drinking water and other activities and this thing helps the researchers to identify the judicious use of time by fisherwomen.

Non-availability of proper marketing

Fish marketing is mostly done by women fishers. Though district Bandipora has a fish market but it doesn't suffice the needs of the bigger fisher population. The study found out that fisherwomen faced problems in marketing the products. Fisherwomen either move from one village to another to sell the fish or spend whole day along the road side for fish selling. Lack of proper fish market makes fish selling a very tedious and cumbersome process. Many fisherwomen can be seen sitting on the road side under the open sky along with their babies to sell the fish. High transportation costs are one of the major challenges faced by fisherwomen in the study area. Greater attention is needed to improve the methods of transporting fish from production centres to various markets. Another significant issue for fisherwomen is the uncertainty in their daily income from sales, as consumer demand for fish can fluctuate, leading to unpredictable earnings.

Conclusions and suggestions

This study focused on the socio-economic status of fisherwomen in the fishing community, found that the respondents in the study area are playing double roles and their living conditions were very miserable and the tedious work nature made their health as worsen. Fisherwomen make substantial contributions to their household income, both directly through the money they earn in market-trading and petty commodity production and indirectly in terms of their unpaid household and agricultural labour, thereby helping significantly to reduce poverty at household and community level. Despite of all

these activities, women's major contribution to household income and expenditure are not being recognised and are continuously dominated by the male folk and their life standard is very poor when compared with other women in Kashmir. The present study clearly articulates that the fisherwomen are in the domain of the socially and economically backward sector of the society. Major problem faced by the fisherwomen were storage and lack of proper transportation and were also exploited by the middle men and in addition the burden of household maintenance. The study found out that all the fisherwomen have some health issues that are related to their fishing activity and work very hard but their socio-economic condition remain same.

*“In order to awaken the people, it is the woman who has to be awakened.
Once she is on the move, the household moves, the village moves,
the country moves and thus we build the India of Tomorrow.”*

Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru

Suggestions to enhance the socio-economic status of the fisherwomen include:

- The government should take proactive steps to educate fisherwomen about their rights.
- Government should also develop good marketing facilities.
- The government, along with private organizations, should encourage fish marketers by creating a structured marketplace that fosters free trade and enhances business opportunities within the study area.
- Government should create awareness about the various governmental schemes from time to time for the welfare of the fishers.
- Government should develop a proper platform where problems encountered by fisherwomen can be brought to the cognizance and addressed.
- Fisherwomen should get support from state and society; families should be provided with incentives to support the industry.

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